

Журнал депонированных рукописей

№5 май, 2004

Труды научно-технической конференции

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"IMPEDANCE" data loggers - new
instrumentation for geophysics and medicine

The research-and-production firm "IMPEDANCE" because of microprocessors creates a series of small-sized digital autonomous systems of data acquisition - universal data loggers (UDL), intended for accumulation and storage for a long time information arriving from various sensors on analog lines. The last achievements in the field of microprocessor engineering have allowed to create a research equipment of the new generation distinguished not only improved characteristics, but also permitting to receive qualitatively new information about processes happening in air and water environments. The built-in microprocessors allow to analyze a received information during a measurement, that allows to proceed from a fixed discrete mode of a measurement to adaptive and by that not only to increase quality of a received information, but also more rationally to use memory size in autonomous devices. Major dignities of microprocessor measuring systems are a possibility of unification of the measuring schemes of instruments and ability of self verification being irreplaceable quality for autonomous stations.

The UDL represent small-sized "Hand-held" - systems, which are constructed because of IBM PC of the compatible processor of a type 80L188EC, are equipped with non-volatile memory and are realized as tight blocks have a low power consumption. The UDL work under the program, which allows operatively to install operational mode registered of performance and the order of inquiry of information lines. Analog signals digitized with the help of built-in ADC. The figures are entered through the sequential interface of a type RS232, which is used also for data transfer in the computer and, if necessary, for loading the specialized program of accumulation and data processing, distinct from delivered. For management of operational mode the UDL are equipped with functional buttons and liquid-crystal indicator.

THE UNIVERSAL DATA LOGGER (model IDL-02) is intended for accumulation and storage of an information arriving from various sensors on analog channels. The saved information in a digital kind is transmitted on the sequential channel to the external computer for consequent processing. The main parameters and operational modes are selected with the help of six functional buttons located on a forward board. or can be

installed program depending on problems of the user. The feed IDL-02 is carried out from accumulators of a type NKMC-3 or from the network adapter. For want of mode power consumption of the power supply realized with application program - impulse of a mode of a feed of all schemes is stipulated to realization of long continuous measurements. A mass of an instruments (without storage batteries) is no more than 1 kilogram.

THE SYSTEM OF DATA COLLECTION (model IDL-03) is intended for accumulation, storage for a long time and transfer to the computer of an information arriving from various sensors on analog channels. The IDL-03 can be applied for want of realizations of seismic and acoustic measurements (in quality 8-channel field portable seismic workstation), for want of realizations of hydrological measurements, for want of realizations of variation multi channel electromagnetic researches and of monitoring works to be used for want of realizations of research works in medicine and magnetobiology. The block diagram IDL-03 is similar IDL-02, however differs by that each measuring channel has a differential input, individual adjustment of an amplification (0... 48 dB) and rebuilt low frequency filter. The possibility of manual or program installation of temporary delay between moment of start and beginning of registration, and also choice of temporary on the basis of average of received data and realization of their digital filtration is stipulated. The feed IDL-03 is carried out from built-in storage batteries or from the power supply of a direct current voltage 7... 24 V.

THE REGISTRAR OF GEOPHYSICAL DATAS (model IDL-04) is intended for registration, storage, processing, analysis and submission of a slow-varying information from eight analog sensors. The IDL-04 includes the block of a measurement and accumulation (BMA) and a magnetic sensitivity converter (MSC), which is connected to the first channel of the BMA with the help of cable of length 6... 10 m. The MSC is executed as the separate module (114 x 80 x 40 mm) because of the fluxgate sensor, has three measuring ranges: 125, 250 and 500 nT and by arranged on the non magnetized rotary system. The IDL-04 realizes the following operations: visualization on the indicator of the schedule "signal - time", transfer of accumulated data through the serial port in the computer, data output in an analog kind on the automatic recorder, manufacturing of "hardcopy" of a screen on the printer, account and demonstrating of an index of magnetic activity. The IDL-04 automatically watch current magnetic perturbations, for the notification about the fixed perturbation the registrar is supplied with the chime. For want of account of magnetic perturbation and index of magnetic activity the data of the registrar are subjected of a digital filtration. Volume of non-volatile memory allows to accumulate data during 14... 113 day. A mass of a device is no more than 3 kilograms.

The UDL IDL-02, IDL-03 and IDL-04 allow to decide a lot of scientific, research and applied problems in geophysics to find broad application for monitoring works realization on a research of an environment to help realization of preventive measures in medicine, can be applied in magnetobiological researches. On the basis of created UDL the construction of autonomous observatories. items of the tax and

accumulation of data, construction of autonomous or marine stations for a measurement of various hydrological and physical fields for want of realizations of works on water areas of the seas and oceans is possible.

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